
Analysis of Energy Footprint of Port Harcourt Metropolis, Nigeria: Implications for Net-Zero

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Abstract

Urban centres are crucial hubs of energy consumption and environmental change, with their ecological footprints (EF) serving as key indicators of sustainability. Understanding the energy use patterns in Port Harcourt (PH) metropolis is critical for guiding efforts toward achieving net-zero emissions. However, such insights remain underexplored in the African context, complicating the development of effective policies. Therefore, this study analyses the energy footprint of PH metropolis using the EF model. Using a descriptive cross-sectional approach, we track annual household consumption across various energy categories, including cooking gas, electricity, charcoal, firewood, and generator usage. The collected data were analysed using SPSS version 23. Findings indicate an energy footprint of 0.003/capita, representing approximately 9.1% of the overall EF for the metropolis, with generator usage accounting for 53.4% of energy consumption. The relatively low energy footprint can be attributed to recent subsidy cuts and rising energy prices, resulting in a decrease in overall energy consumption. Results further reveal a shift towards energy transition, with Liquefied Petroleum Gas accounting for 36% of the energy footprint. Our study highlights the significant impact of fossil fuel consumption on the energy footprint in the PH metropolis and calls for policies that prioritise investments in renewable energy infrastructure, developing off-grid energy solutions, upgrading the national electricity grid, and promoting the adoption of cleaner fuel alternatives.

Keywords: Ecological footprint, Energy consumption, Energy transition, Net-Zero, Sustainability, Urbanisation

1 Introduction

Urbanisation is a global phenomenon with profound environmental implications, particularly through its influence on energy consumption and ecological degradation. As cities grow, their energy demand intensifies, often leading to increased reliance on fossil fuels and unsustainable resource exploitation (Lu and Chen, 2017; Nathaniel *et al.*, 2019; Khan *et al.*, 2023). As cities expand spatially and demographically, their demand for energy in the transport, industry, and household sectors intensifies (Nathaniel, 2020; Nathaniel *et al.*, 2020), often outpacing infrastructural and policy responses designed to ensure sustainable development. This dynamic is effectively captured by the concept of ecological footprint (EF), which measures the biologically productive land and water area required to support a population's consumption and absorb its waste, including carbon emissions from energy use (Rees & Wackernagel, 1996). The EF has become a widely accepted metric for assessing the sustainability of urban development (Swiader *et al.*, 2017), particularly in rapidly expanding cities in the Global South.

Numerous studies have demonstrated that energy consumption significantly impacts urban EF, particularly in developing countries where infrastructure lacks optimal energy efficiency (Babatunde *et al.*, 2020). In China, for example, fossil fuel usage accounted for nearly 90% of the EF in resource-intensive cities, such as Fushun, highlighting the environmental consequences of industrial urbanisation (Wu *et al.*, 2011). Similarly, Hardi *et al.* (2024) found that both the shadow economy and energy consumption substantially contributed to the increase in Indonesia's EF. In a related study, Nathaniel (2020) observed that high energy usage increases Indonesia's EF figures in both the short and long term. Supporting this finding, Khan and Hou (2020) identified a positive correlation between per capita energy consumption and EF levels. These studies highlight the increasing challenges that cities face and the need to strike a balance between energy demand and environmental sustainability.

However, despite the relatively low per capita EFs in many African cities, including those in Nigeria, due to lower overall consumption, heavy reliance on fossil fuel-based energy poses significant ecological threats. Studies indicate that urban households in Africa depend heavily on fossil fuels, contributing to forest degradation and carbon emissions (Ahmed *et al.*, 2019; Nathaniel *et al.*, 2019), which exacerbates environmental stress, particularly in urbanising regions where energy poverty restricts access to cleaner alternatives. Port Harcourt, one of Nigeria's most industrialised and rapidly urbanising cities, serves as a critical case for examining the ecological implications of urban energy consumption. As a hub for petroleum-related activities, the city's energy demands are driven by the residential, commercial, and industrial sectors. However, there is limited empirical evidence on how these energy patterns translate into ecological pressure using comprehensive metrics, such as EF. While previous studies have explored broader national or regional dynamics in countries such as South Africa and India (Nathaniel *et al.*, 2019; Khan *et al.*, 2023), a significant gap remains in city-specific EF assessments within Nigeria.

Therefore, this study addresses this gap by analysing the EF of energy consumption in the Port Harcourt metropolis. By applying the EF model, this research quantifies the environmental cost of energy use in the city, identifies key contributing factors, and explores implications for sustainable urban planning. By situating Port Harcourt within broader discourses on urban sustainability and ecological metabolism, this research contributes to the emerging literature, offering crucial insights for informing energy and environmental policy, particularly in alignment with the country's commitment to sustainable development and net-zero ambition.

2 Materials and Method

2.1 Study Area

The Port Harcourt (PH) metropolitan area encompasses the Port Harcourt and Obio-Akpor Local Government Areas (Elekwachi *et al.*, 2019), with the Port Harcourt City Local Government Area serving as the administrative centre of Rivers State. According to the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) (2007), the population of PH City was estimated at 1,000,908. However, recent estimates indicate that the population has increased to approximately 1,439,600 (City Population, 2023), affirming its status as one of Nigeria's four most populous cities and one of the nation's fastest-growing urban areas. As the hub of the oil and gas industry, PH faces environmental challenges due to industrial activities and rapid urban expansion, making it an ideal location for evaluating the energy footprint and its impact on the environmental sustainability of Nigeria's rapidly expanding urban centres.

2.2 Study Design and Data Collection

We employed a descriptive cross-sectional approach to assess yearly household consumption across various energy categories, including cooking gas, electricity, charcoal, firewood, and generator usage. This assessment was conducted using the EF questionnaire, which was adapted from Khan and Hussain (2017) and tailored to suit the local conditions. The gathered data were supplemented with conversion factors, emission standards, and yield and equivalent factors (Table 1), sourced from both national and international research bodies, including the Global Footprint Network (GFN), the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), and the Nigerian Bureau of Statistics (NBS).

Table 1 Emission Factor Derivation and Sources

S/N	Variable	Emission factor	Source
1.	Electricity	0.439kgC02/kwh	Sam-Amobi <i>et al.</i> , 2019
2.	LPG	3.03 kgco ₂ /kg	MoE (2015)
3.	Firewood	1.59 kgco ₂ /kg	Bhattacharya <i>et al.</i> 2002
4.	Charcoal	2.36 kgco ₂ /kg	Bhattacharya <i>et al.</i> 2002
5.	Petrol	19.35t/gallon	Doulabi & Hejazi, 2018
6.	Diesel	10.9kg/gallon	Carbon independent, 2023
7.	Sequestration factor	1.6175tco ₂ /acre/yr	Khan & Uddin, 2018
8.	Forest Land	1.26	GFN (2018)
9.	Carbon	1.26	GFN (2018)

2.3 Sampling Protocol

According to Eq. 1 (Nishat, 2021), the sample size was determined to be 384 households per city, with a 5% margin of error and 95% confidence level. To compensate for potential non-responses and incomplete data, we increased the sample size by 30%, resulting in a final estimated sample size of 500 households. Of these, 479 were successfully surveyed, yielding a response rate of 95.8%. We then utilised a two-stage stratified random sampling method, first selecting urban local government areas (LGAs) and subsequently dividing them into political wards. Four wards were randomly selected, and within each ward, households were systematically sampled at every fifth house to participate in the survey.

$$n = \frac{z^2 \times p(1-p)}{e^2} / 1 + \left(\frac{z^2 \times p(1-p)}{e^2 N} \right) \quad (1)$$

where n is the sample size, N is the population size, e is the error margin of 5% (0.05), p is the standard deviation (0.5), and z is the z -score of 1.96 at the 95% confidence level.

2.4 Data Analysis

Data analysis was conducted using SPSS 23.0, and descriptive statistics were employed to summarise the quantitative results. The EF was calculated using the mathematical functions outlined in the subsequent subsections.

2.5 Energy Footprint Estimation

Calculating the energy footprint involves considering the carbon emissions resulting from the burning of fossil fuels for various household activities. We adopted the bottom-up EF approach described by Khan and Uddin (2018). Therefore, in this study, the estimation of the energy footprint was based on the energy consumption patterns of five primary household activities in the study area: electricity usage, liquefied petroleum gas (LPG), generator use, and the consumption of firewood and charcoal, as detailed below:

2.5.1 Electricity Consumption

We evaluated electricity usage by analysing the average monthly electricity bills gathered from households during the survey period. To determine the annual electricity consumption in kilowatt-hours (kWh), the yearly expenditure was divided by the electricity unit price for Rivers State, which was 61.40/kWh (NERC, 2023). The carbon emissions produced were then divided by the carbon sequestration factor, measured in tons of CO₂ per acre per year, to calculate the annual acreage required to offset the emitted carbon (Khan & Uddin, 2018). The annual value in hectares was derived by multiplying the initial figure by the conversion factor and subsequently converting it to global hectares (gha) using a forest land equivalent factor (GFN, 2018; Khan & Uddin, 2018). Consequently, the EF of electricity was determined using Eq. 2 (Khan & Uddin, 2018).

$$EF_e = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{C \times F_c}{S_f} \times C_f \times E_f \quad (2)$$

Where C represents annual electricity consumption (kWh), F_c is the emission factor for CO₂ (tonsCO₂/kWh), S_f is the carbon sequestration factor (tonsCO₂/acre/year), C_f is the conversion factor for hectares, and E_f is the Equivalent factor, which translates a specific type of land (forest) into the global hectare, a standard unit of bio-productivity.

Table 2 Consumption footprint data requirements and data sources

S/N	Items	Average price	Source
16	Electricity (PH)	61.40/Kwh	NERC (2023)
17	Petrol	626.21/L	NBS (2023a)
18	Diesel	890.80/L	NBS (2023b)
19	LPG	837.99/kg	NBS (2023c)
20	Charcoal	342.72/kg	Oak Intelligence, 2024
21	Firewood	695/kg	Oak Intelligence, 2024

2.5.2 LPG

Household gas consumption was estimated using survey data, either based on the amount of gas used or the yearly expenditure on household gas, which was then converted into

kilograms by dividing by the price for the reference year (837.99/kg) (NBS, 2023a). Subsequently, the total annual gas consumption in kilograms was converted into carbon emissions by multiplying it by the standard emission factor (Khan & Uddin, 2018). The carbon emissions, measured in tons of CO₂/kg, were then converted to annual acres by dividing by the sequestration factor and further transformed into annual global hectares by multiplying the result by the conversion factor for hectares and the equivalent factor for forestland. Ultimately, the EF for LPG from household use was computed using Eq. 3 (Khan & Uddin, 2018).

$$EF_{ng} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{C \times Fc}{Sf} \times Cf \times Ef \quad (3)$$

Where C is the annual gas consumption (kg), Fc is the emission factor for gas (tonsCO₂/kg), Sf is the carbon sequestration factor (tonsCO₂/acre/year), Cf is the conversion factor for hectares, and Ef is the equivalent factor of forest land.

2.5.3 Generator Usage

Generating sets is a significant source of household energy and significantly contributes to fuel consumption. To determine the impact of generator use, the annual fuel expenditure was calculated by dividing it by the petrol price per litre (626.21/L) (NBS, 2023b) and diesel price per litre (890.80/L) (NBS, 2023c). This provided the yearly fuel consumption in litres, which was then converted to gallons by dividing by 3.7853 (Doulabi & Hejazi, 2018). The carbon emissions per gallon were determined using conversion standards. Finally, the generator consumption footprint is calculated using Eq. 4 (Khan & Uddin, 2018) by applying sequestration and equivalency factors (refer to Table 2).

$$EF = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{C \times Fc}{Sf} \times Cf \times Ef \quad (4)$$

Where C is the annual fuel (diesel and petrol) consumption (Gallon), Fc is the emission factor for respective fuel type (kg C02/gallon), Sf is the carbon sequestration factor (tonsCO₂/acre/year), Cf is the conversion factor for hectare and Ef is the equivalent factor.

2.5.4 Firewood and Charcoal Consumption

Additionally, the majority of Nigerian households rely predominantly on firewood and charcoal as their primary energy sources, especially for cooking, mainly due to the high cost of energy. Consequently, the carbon footprint of firewood and charcoal was determined by calculating the annual spending on these fuels and multiplying by the emission factor, which yields the amount of CO₂ in tons (Khan & Uddin, 2018). Ultimately, the footprints for firewood and charcoal usage were calculated using Eq. 5 (Khan & Uddin, 2018) by multiplying the sequestration and equivalency factors, respectively (Table 2).

$$EF = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{C \times Fc}{Sf} \times Cf \times Ef \quad (5)$$

Where C is the annual firewood/charcoal consumption (kg), Fc is the emission factor for the respective fuel type (kg C02/kg), Sf is the carbon sequestration factor (tonsCO₂/acre/year), Cf is the conversion factor for hectare and Ef is the equivalent factor.

3 Results and Discussion

This study analyses the EF of PH metropolis using the EF model and assesses its broader implications for environmental sustainability. The results indicate an energy footprint of 0.003/capita, representing approximately 9.1% of the overall EF for the metropolis, making it the third-largest contributor to the total EF (see Figure 1). This highlights the substantial impact of energy consumption on the urban EF. This finding can be attributed to the dependence on fossil-fuel-based energy sources, which account for over two-thirds of the total energy footprint. This disparity emphasises the urgent need for continued investment in renewable energy infrastructure to mitigate the environmental impacts associated with the energy sector (see Figure 1).

In the PH metropolis, backup generators play a significant role in the energy footprint, accounting for 53.4% of energy consumption. This is primarily due to the unreliable electricity supply and frequent power outages. This situation underscores the reliance on off-grid energy solutions, such as generators, to meet the energy demands of urban areas in Nigeria. However, this dependence also raises concerns regarding carbon emissions and their effects on the overall energy footprint. Previous studies have demonstrated that the use of fossil fuels significantly contributes to CO₂ emissions, thereby affecting the EF (Shahbaz *et al.*, 2013; Anser, 2019; Chen *et al.*, 2019; Abbas *et al.*, 2021). These findings underscore the need for evidence-based policies that promote energy efficiency in alignment with national and global sustainability goals.

In comparison, the findings of this study mirror a broader global trend, in which the energy footprint contributes only modestly to the overall EF of urban cities. Previous research has identified a low energy footprint in other cities, such as those in developing Asian countries (Sharma *et al.*, 2021), South Asian Economies, such as China (Xue *et al.*, 2021), and Ijebu-Ode, Nigeria (Sawyer *et al.*, 2023), which is consistent with the results of the current study. The relatively low energy footprint in the PH metropolis (9.1%) can be attributed to recent subsidy cuts and rising energy prices, resulting in a reduction in overall energy consumption. For example, data from the reference year indicate a 32% decrease in daily fuel consumption following the removal of subsidies (Musa & Abubakar, 2024). This trend aligns with Wang's (2018) argument that while industrial growth increases energy usage, reducing consumption intensity can mitigate its overall environmental impact.

In contrast, the findings of this study differ from those of Begum & Pereira (2012), who identified energy as the significant contributor to EF in Malaysia (53%). This discrepancy may arise from differences in the primary energy sources used and their affordabilities. In their study, energy subsidies led to higher consumption due to increased energy affordability, which in turn boosted demand. It has been observed that greater access to energy sources often correlates with higher levels of energy consumption (Pachauri & Spreng, 2004). Consequently, numerous studies have emphasised that increased energy consumption leads to higher CO₂ emissions and a larger ecological footprint (Tiba & Omri, 2017), with fossil fuels being a significant contributor to the rise in CO₂ emissions and EF (Anser, 2019; Szigeti *et al.*, 2017).

Fig. 1 Energy footprint by consumption categories in PH metropolis

Electricity consumption accounts for 10.4% of the energy footprint, a statistic that aligns with trends observed in most urban areas of Nigeria (Oyedepo, 2012; Mukhtar *et al.*, 2021), primarily due to the unreliability of the national grid. Studies have shown that electricity usage generally has a lower impact on EF as it often results in reduced carbon emissions (Borisade *et al.*, 2020; Sharif *et al.*, 2020). This underscores the urgent need for policy reforms to enhance the national grid and to ensure a stable and sustainable electricity supply.

Further observations have revealed a notable shift towards energy transition, highlighted by the significant consumption of Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG), which accounts for 36% of the energy footprint. This trend aligns with the federal government's efforts to promote green energy solutions. The current findings support those of Ojo and Abd'Razack (2018), who reported that LPG consumption accounted for 9% of the energy footprint in Bida, Nigeria. LPG is recognised for its low carbon emissions and minimal impact on the energy footprint (Xue *et al.*, 2021), emphasising the need for policies that encourage the widespread adoption of LPG in households as part of the transition to cleaner energy sources.

Policy Implications for Nigeria's Energy Transition Drive

The findings of this study underscore the urgent need for Nigeria to adopt a more comprehensive and strategic approach to energy transition. First, it is crucial to prioritise investments in renewable energy infrastructure, including solar, wind, and hydroelectric power. By shifting from fossil fuel-based energy sources to cleaner alternatives, Nigeria can significantly reduce its carbon emissions and bolster its long-term energy security. Additionally, there is a pressing need to develop off-grid energy solutions, such as solar mini-grids and efficient battery storage systems, particularly in urban areas where grid power is unreliable. This strategy would reduce the country's current dependence on polluting backup generators, which are significant contributors to the country's energy-related environmental challenges.

Moreover, upgrading the national electricity grid is crucial to reduce reliance on off-grid power solutions. Policies aimed at enhancing grid stability, expanding its reach, and ensuring a dependable power supply will not only lessen the need for fossil fuel-powered generators but also promote a more sustainable energy mix. Similarly, the government should implement and advocate policies that encourage the widespread adoption of cleaner fuel alternatives such as Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG), particularly in households. Enacting these policy measures will not only facilitate Nigeria's energy transition but also bolster its broader efforts to combat climate change and promote long-term sustainability.

Limitations of the Study

While this study offers valuable insights into the energy footprint of the PH metropolis, it is crucial to acknowledge its limitations. First, the analysis was based on data collected from a single metropolitan area, which may not fully capture the diverse energy consumption patterns present in other parts of Nigeria. Consequently, the findings may not apply to all Nigerian cities or rural regions, where energy usage and sources may differ significantly. Second, the study's reliance on secondary data, such as fuel consumption statistics and energy usage reports, introduces potential limitations in terms of data accuracy and completeness. In some cases, the data might be outdated or incomplete, particularly in rural areas, where energy consumption patterns are less documented. This could affect the reliability of the conclusions regarding the energy footprint of a metropolis. Lastly, the study's temporal scope is limited to a specific timeframe; therefore, it does not account for potential changes in energy consumption patterns resulting from future shifts in energy policies, technological advancements, or global economic conditions. As a result, these findings may not fully reflect long-term trends in energy consumption.

Despite its limitations, this study provides data-driven insights that can inform energy policy and decision-making in Nigeria, particularly in urban areas, and suggests further research to gain a thorough understanding of Nigeria's energy footprint.

Conclusion

This study analyses the energy footprint of the PH metropolis, emphasising the crucial role that energy consumption plays in shaping a region's overall environmental sustainability. Findings indicate that energy consumption accounts for 9.1% of the city's total energy footprint, with fossil fuel-based energy sources, particularly backup generators, being the primary contributors. This highlights the necessity for a transition towards more sustainable energy practices, including the adoption of renewable energy sources and the expansion of off-grid energy solutions to tackle the challenges posed by unreliable electricity supply. Our findings demonstrate the significant impact of fossil fuel consumption on the energy footprint in the PH metropolis, while also identifying emerging opportunities for energy transition through the adoption of cleaner energy sources such as LPG. Therefore, there is a need for evidence-based policies and strategic investments in renewable energy infrastructure to further reduce the energy footprint and promote long-term environmental sustainability.

Competing Interest

None

Funding

None

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